

Illustration Design Based on Local Cultural Elements: Case study of Nimba Mask Guinea Conakry

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This research paper responds to the associated research problem in illustration Design, based on local culture element specifically how to improve Nimba mask Illustration in my country. According to the poor art illustration, so many domains but basically creativity which helps improve culture, entertainment, economic and social side, has been an issue and a big challenge for Guineans citizen. This framework is then used to undertake a close analysis of its improvement based the research questions. The introduction will talk about the generality of our art object (Nimba Mask) in my country I mean the overview, then I'll move to the study purpose which can make clear the goal that need to be reached at the end of the research and so far the research objectives and questions will be based on summarizing the accomplishment and those questions that I need to wonder so that the article will be completed efficiently. The opinion of people about the improvement of Nimba Mask analyzing it's by using the qualitative method of design and conclude through what I have above afterward.

Keywords: NIMBA MASK, DESIGN, ILLUSTRATION, GUINEA CONAKRY

Introduction

An illustration is a decoration, interpretation or visual explanation of a text, concept or process, designed for integration in print and digital published media, such as posters, flyers, magazines, books, teaching materials, animations, video games and films. Those illustrations can also be a visualization or a depiction made by an artist, such as a drawing, sketch, painting, photograph, or other kind of image of things seen, remembered or imagined, using a graphical representation. Illustration design has become a viral way in so many domains

such as Entertainment, promotional materials, national events, packaging, and stories to mention but a few. This proves that illustration design depending on the context of the information that needs visual representation, it can also help determine the personality of the design no matter their form or color (Larson, 2019). They can convey moods or emotions present in any kind of illustration work. It is critical for individuals in charge of their project to understand the value of illustration and why illustrations are preferable to video and images. The most crucial part of any illustration is the best illustration that can express the proper message in the most clear and easy manner. You may strengthen the idea of any piece of writing with the use of photos and drawings, whether it's for illustrating a tale or providing learning material for medical writing. Furthermore, illustration is important in promoting or advertising products for a firm, as the artist develops the visuals of the products.

Illustrate a Message- If you wish to express a difficult-to-describe and-explain concept, pictures might be really useful. It is a proven truth that the human brain processes visual information in such a way that it experiences it fully, rapidly, and retains it for a longer period of time. These are several technologically advanced pictures, flowcharts, and sketches that can be quite useful for those with short attention spans and hearing impairments.

Education- Illustrations and various types of pictures have been used for educational purposes since the dawn of time. Aside from that, pictures are employed to teach and develop the imagination of children. This is one of the reasons why having outstanding illustrations for children's books is so important. Furthermore, drawings aid in the association of words with phrases and objects with pictorial actions by children. Additionally, graphics are ingeniously made and developed to entice children to read. Illustrations are extensively utilized to teach people of all ages, particularly when it comes to technical principles, scientific presentations, foreign languages, and a variety of other topics. Illustrations can be used to highlight important information. It's the first thing someone notices, even before reading the words next to the graphic.

Nimba Mask

Nimba mask known as one of the best and attractive art sculpture in the Museum of African Arts, and also most intriguing, hence the name Nimba. This piece was among the first to be aquatinted by Veda and Dr Zdravko Pecar for their collection which forms the base of the present-day museum. This headdress is unique in the art of the Africans. It originates among the Baga people living in Guinea, in the most western parts of the African continent. The Nimba was employed in rice harvest dance ceremonies performed in order to procure the fertility of the fields, (Museum of African Art, 2020). Nimba is assumed to represent a divinity of abundance and fertility, but the precise interpretation is yet to be obtained. It is also linked with pregnant women, and those wishing to secure their progeny. The dancer carried it on his shoulders, holding the piece by its front legs, while his whole body was adorned in a costume made of vegetal fibers.

The art illustration of Nimba mask started since 1986 when the Guinea army over take the power and became the governing (after the death of Guinea formal President Ahmed Sekou Toure) that illustration work has being made or sponsored by Guinea government in the date mention above. The illustration design work of Nimba Mask was drawn for the first time on the 5 thousand banknote in 1985 then drawn on same 5 thousand in 1998, 2006 and 2012 , in 2015 it was drawn because a new design came up it was not only design on the 5 thousand banknote also the 50 coin made 1985. The illustration design supposed to be more existing than just putting an art object image on banknote illustration contain more specific things such as pattern graphic design, motion design, book cover, T-shirt design, album art and so on. The application of Nimba Mask illustration in the above stated country specially using it as one of the famous mask in the world, the main aim is to use most of the illustration design on Nimba mask which can improve culture, economics, technology specially education in that specific context.

The illustration work will be based on how to apply graphic pattern textiles design T-shirt design, book cover, picture books, motion design and album art, each one of them will be related to the application of Nimba mask illustration art work and his impact on modern illustration.

Figure 1: Nimba Mask

Materials and methods

The identification of works of art object through the general procedures as determining the treatment needed to restore a damaged item or improve its value. The art historian, designers or creator discover who was the actual executor of a particular sculpture object. This work project is particularly significant when it comes to a large sums of public interest and value which are to be committed to a major purpose of the country's improvement in art, culture and economic. The question is how to determine their authenticity and well their identification which is a significant challenge for the country cultural image. Often the claim proves to be unsubstantiated, but there is always a chance of discovering the greatest on every art object.

The main objective of this project is to make sure that most of graphic design illustration work will be used on Nimba Mask in order to illustrate its design appearance which can improve culture, economics, technology specially education in that specific context which make the design more existing than just putting an art object image on banknote, illustration contain more specific things such as pattern graphic design, motion design, book cover, T-shirt design, album art and so on. With the rise of the technology PS Photoshop and adobe illustration have eased the illustration design and materiels required, it's because the entire design is made on the software mention above (Adobe Photoshop)

Figure: 2 Expected logo

This project is going to generate the modernization to fellow young people working in our cultural Minister to change their general view through our art history in other to better the future.

This figure illustrate how I want Nimba Mask to be identified in my country because Making it as the identification of Guinea culture is not an easy thing but knowing the reputation and the power which cover its can help. According to [Curtis and Sarro, \(1997\)](#) Nimba mask has to be printed on most of our objects, secondly organizing event which help people remind its power and importance for human more importantly women such exhibition and so on. This will bring a lot of joy in our community but also give influence to the Nimba Mask in and out of the country, boost our economic and push tourist to come and discover our culture which also help the country to make cultural exchange with different countries through tourist.

Result and Discussion

My project presents the finding of qualitative bell component that consist of a series of semi-structured interviews with women and men of various groups of age and education level in all the aspect of my country, who recently have worked on Nimba Mask and still working on it. They will be asked about learning experience, the reason why they engaged in art illustration more importantly the Mask mentioned above and also its benefits in education and daily life. This is the crucial part of benefit as well as, joy learning, motivation

and achievement (Shoulder helmet mask, 2005).

This project will bring creativity in my community and motivate them to explore complex dimensional especially in children side by including Art and design learning material according to the variety of purpose such as.

- explaining complex and challenging concept in easy to comprehend manner.
- include in our educational system the learning of Nimba mask (syllabus).
- make learning more enjoyable experience for even poorly performing students.
- presenting things in completely new perspective
- making visualization more interesting such as text, image, gesture so on.
- surmounting the age barrier in learning modern and old art design of the country (Nimba Mask).

The global market value of the art in the world is considerable, knowing its importance in each country for their image and history, most countries reach their economic goals through their arts objects by creating museums, or putting value on touristic places which make the economy grow according to the power, influence and how important is your art object. Fagg, (1961) emphasized on the influence and power of my country art object likely Nimba Mask which can help create graphic illustration, developing art design purpose, those will develop the economies and huge the potential market owing to subsidies and the tax rebates being offering by the government to encourage the illustration design without forgetting the technology sector also widely use to inform, educate, entertain people and research facilities for all those domains participating for economy improvement.

Conclusion

I have come to analyze that, my project in Illustration design based on a local element that the study purpose is the improvement of Nimba Mask in my country, so through those interviews I have concluded at the end that art illustration has been proven by numerous studies as a medium conducive to facilitate art history learning in study area. However, Illustration design through Nimba Mask can be put to various creative uses for complementing different segments as I mention above. It is useful for accomplishing desired objectives in streamlined manner. In the educational sector and economy. I can develop and deliver my country along with supportive art history elements for taking teaching and Art history pursuit to the next level. The lesson can motivate learners and promote their potential to fulfill our art innovation dreams through this project.

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